

VALKYRIES

D1.6 Ethics and diversity compliance report

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on ethics and diversity compliance requirements met from the VALKYRIES Consortium during the project.

The deliverable includes a demo with scenarios to be broadly used while developing technological solutions for first responders.

The demo will be shared in open access on the VALKIRIES website.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Ethics and diversity compliance report

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3. Document and Project Scope

This document answers harmonisation and standardisation needs in the field of compliance activities impacting on the whole life-cycle of the research and in particular on the ethical legal issues related to non-discrimination and diversity issues.

3.1. Project Overview

VALKYRIES aims to develop standardised and harmonised procedures for first responders. In this frame, ethical legal issues shall be addressed by design to support any step of the technological development. For this reason, this deliverable will contribute to identify, assess and extract harmonised practices for innovators.

3.2. Document Structure

This document includes a general overview of the methodological approach towards ethics and diversity compliance; the description of the issues emerged in the project; the extraction of guidelines and best practices for innovators. The document includes a web-based demonstrator (DEMO).

4. Ethics and diversity compliance report

4.1. Methodological remarks

Challenges to diversity protection are many: they include non-discriminatory actions aiming to prevent prejudices occur as well as those positive actions aiming to support diversity in a given environment.

To this end, we design this deliverable in a double perspective: firstly, as a compliance activity addressed within VALKYRIES consortium during the entire life-cycle of the research; secondly, as an opportunity to develop a more inclusive environment within a project Consortium, addressing ethics and diversity as a management tool.

The two perspectives have been addressed through a bottom-up approach developed with a series of initiatives aiming to analyse the ethics and diversity-related issues both in VALKYRIES project and in general in Research and Innovation sector. In particular, we developed the following initiatives:

1. We performed a **continuous ethical-legal assessment** of the project activities. The ethical-legal unit (SSSA), in fact, is involved in all the WPs to address the following issues and detect ethics and diversity challenges in terms of compliance.
2. We provided an analysis on the contents of the **Gender Equality Plans** adopted by the individual partners of the consortium.
3. We provided the collection of **ethics and diversity needs** from the Consortium in order to assess perceived barriers to ethics and diversity as well as possible strategies to prevent and deal with possible issues.

The one-to-one and plenary consulting activities under sub 1 has been undertaken during the development of tasks, deliverables, etc allowing to shape a concrete overview of sensitive topics, sectors, and challenges within the VALKYRIES ecosystem. Together with the collection of data under sub 2 and 3 we explored how to address the ethics and diversity challenges both in VALKYRIES and, more generally, in a research Consortium as well as to discuss how to develop efficient solutions to be practically implemented in a web-based tool.

4.2. Ethics and Diversity analysis

Such an analysis starts from the premises that strictly compliance activities are considered to develop a cultural change aiming to undertake a more ethical and inclusive research *by design*, by promoting good practices.

For the purposes of this deliverable, in order to avoid overlapping with other tasks under WP 1, 3 and 8, we will focus only on the following grounds: gender-related issues and other diversity related issues.

1. **Gender-related issues** we mean, according to the European Institute for Gender Equality – EIGE (2014) notion: *“all aspects and concerns related to women’s and men’s lives and situation in society, to the way they interrelate, their differences in access to and use of resources, their activities, and how they react to changes, interventions and policies”*¹.

¹ European Institute for Gender Equality – EIGE (2014). Effectiveness of Institutional Mechanisms for the Advancement of Gender Equality: Review of the Implementation of the Beijing Platform for Action in the EU Member States.

2. **Other diversity-related issues** with the aim to reduce bias under all possible grounds of discrimination. In this context, we apply the grounds of discrimination according to article 9 of the EU Regulation General Data Protection Regulation “GDPR” notion of special categories of personal data as those ones that are “revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership (...) genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation”.

4.2.1. Continuous ethical-legal assessment

As anticipated, the continuous ethical legal assessment for gender-related and other diversity-related issues has been undertaken by providing ethical legal advice during the life-cycle of the VALKYRIES research to meet also other compliance requirements as well as to develop a more inclusive culture within the consortium.

The following issues have been addressed in the first year of the project in terms of human resources and activities management:

1. To promote the gender balance within the appointments to be distributed in the project. For example, during the Kick of Meeting 2 women have been appointed respectively as innovation manager and communication manager.
2. To promote a better work-life balance during the management of the project. For example, calls and meetings have been scheduled combining family needs (e.g., avoiding / limiting schools breaks) and agenda have been followed taking into account possible individual needs of family care.

In the development of technical tasks, instead, gender-related and diversity issues have been addressed as follows.

1. In the development of questionnaires delivered to first responders: no reference to gender identity / sexual orientation has been included in light of the principle of minimization under article 5 GDPR. In fact, the consortium considered as not relevant such an information for the purposes of the task.
2. The Consortium considered that as far as data collection in the context of the developed Minimum Dataset for the victims, information regarding sex and pregnancy status will be processed for healthcare purposes and management only.

In the development of AI-based solutions, gender-related and diversity issues are considered following the EU Commission strategy for a Trustworthy AI.

In particular, the harmonisation and standardisation actions for innovators cannot avoid the current debate on technologies assessment under the ethics, lawfulness and robustness pillars identified by the High-Level Group on AI. In parallel to the proposal on AI Regulation, in fact, a series of tools and checklists have been developed to address the compliance activities in an ethically manner by design and by default. The so-called Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) checklist, for instance, drives the developers through a questionnaire of 63 questions addressing seven grounds of analysis that include, among all, also diversity, non-discrimination and fairness. The latter aims to avoid unfair bias and to ensure accessibility and universal design, including stakeholders’ participation in the development steps. In this regard, VALKYRIES project addressed these requirements as follows.

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?	The VALKYRIES project aims to prevent bias by providing balanced samples to the algorithms, aiming to generate unbiased models.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data? Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use cases? Did you research and use publicly available technical bias that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance? Did you assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness)? O Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?	The project considers training models with a balanced number of users, taking into consideration diversity characteristics of the society. It also considers the use of state-of-the-art techniques to ensure that data is well balanced and provide biased results.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system?	The designers and developers of the project have been helped through many meetings to understand the consequences of unfair bias and possible solutions to avoid it.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Did you ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or performance of the AI system? O Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised? O Did you identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end-)users and/or subjects?	VALKYRIES considers some mechanism obtained from experience and state-of-the-art in order to prevent the generation of biased models. It has also established clear step and ways of communication which has been studied in depth by all contributors and end-users. The project identifies as subjects that could be affected all the entities that belong to this.
Avoidance of unfair bias	Is your definition of fairness commonly used and implemented in any step the process of setting up the AI system? Did you consider other definitions of fairness before choosing	The definition proposed by VALKYRIES is being applied in all phases of models generation.

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
	<p>this one? Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e. representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities? Did you ensure a quantitative or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness? O Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system?</p>	<p>The project also identified many possible definitions before choosing the one which is being used It consulted with all the entities on which this project depends and to which it is addressed. The project performed many tests to check if the definition used is valid, applying balanced samples and techniques provided by state-of-the-art. VALKYRIES establishes mechanisms that allow to guarantee the fairness through tests and studies of the generated models.</p>
Accessibility and Universal Design	<p>Did you ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society?</p>	<p>The project has raised the awareness of all entities in charge of the AI system so that it can correspond to preferences and abilities in society.</p>
Accessibility and Universal Design	<p>Did you assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? O Did you ensure that information about, and the AI system's user interface of, the AI system is accessible and usable also to users of assistive technologies (such as screen readers)? O Did you involve or consult with end-users or subjects in need for assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the AI system?</p>	<p>The AI system user interface has been designed and implemented with the objective of making it easy for all people to use. Moreover, the project ensured that every user who needs help to use the AI system user interface since it implemented assistive technologies such as screen readers, text readers and speech input software.</p>
Accessibility and Universal Design	<p>Did you ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if possible?</p>	<p>VALKYRIES considered the use of Universal Design principles during all Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC) phases.</p>
Accessibility and Universal Design	<p>Did you take the impact the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account? Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system engaged with the target end-users and/or subjects? Did you assess whether there could be</p>	<p>The project always considers the possible consequences, both positive and negative, that may be caused by the AI system.</p>

ALTAI Requirements	Questions to be addressed	Implemented actions and relevant task
	groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the AI system? Did you assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-user's or subject's communities?	It also evaluated that designer and developer are involved with the target in order to check if the requirements are correct and new requirements are needed. VAKYRIES project took into account that those people with disabilities could be the most affected for the results. For this reason, it has been provided with mechanisms to avoid this problem. It also evaluated the possible risks and it established mechanism so that the risk is avoided or minimized.
Stakeholder Participation	Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development?	The project considered that the communication with many stakeholders allows to know new useful requirements that have to be implemented.

Table 1 – ALTAI requirements

4.2.2. Gender Equality Plans analysis

Among the partners, we collected and analysed the following Gender Equality Plans (GEP) in order to identify analogies and differences as well as to extract possible best practices to be applied in the Consortium strategy for ethics and diversity issues management.

The following table summarises the grounds of the undertaken analysis.

AREA	Objectives	How VALKYRIES supported these Actions
Work-life balance	Support for the reconciliation of work and private life	Work organisation tailored to family needs
	Adoption of the gender perspective in organizational culture	Supporting women recruited in the project
	Adoption an inclusive language protocol	Adoption of gender-neutral language
	Building an inclusive work and study environment	Adoption of inclusive strategies during formal and informal activities
	To promote feminine leadership among the Administration and Services Staff	Project Boards have been gender balanced
Gender balance in	Harmonization of decision-making processes and internal sources	Project Boards have been gender balanced

AREA	Objectives	How VALKYRIES supported these Actions
top positions and in decision-making bodies	with the activities included in the GEP	
	Promote equal opportunities in culture, processes and institutional practices	Project Boards have been gender balanced
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Improvement of equal opportunities in academic recruitment	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Improvement of equal opportunities in career progression	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To transmit the commitment to gender equality and non-discrimination	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Job stability and promotion	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To reduce the pay gap	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
Integration of the gender dimension in research and teaching programs	Promotion of the integration of sex and gender variables in the research process	Ethical-legal impact assessment in the development of the VALKYRIES ecosystem
	Promote the integration of a gender dimension in teaching content	N/A
	To transmit the commitment to gender equality and non-discrimination through the University's	N/A
	Showcasing and encouraging research with a gender perspective	Website contents highlight the gender perspective in VALKYRIES development and management
Tackling gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Contribute to the reduction of gender prejudices and stereotypes	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Raise awareness on issues related to gender equality within the community of the organisation and outside it, also contributing to the deconstruction of gender stereotypes	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	Prevent, identify and manage cases of sexual harassment between teaching staff, technical staff and administrative, students and female students	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures

AREA	Objectives	How VALKYRIES supported these Actions
	To showcase resources against harassment	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
Encouraging diversity and inclusion	Everyone shall perform at its best in order to ensure that workforce grows and remains diverse in regards to cultures, gender, generation, abilities and other capacities	Compliance to the internal codes of ethics/gender equality plans in recruitment procedures
	To guarantee balanced presence on governing bodies and representation	Issue addressed during KoM

Table 2 – GEPs analysis

4.2.3. Ethics and diversity needs

In order to detect ethics and diversity needs among the Consortium, we mapped its composition, the adoption of an internal GEP and the emerged gender-related issues in VALKYRIES.

The table below summarises the results of the data collection on gender-related issues.

Partner	Team composition	Gender Equality Plan	Gender related issues	Adopted strategy
SSSA	1 M (including unit coordinator) 5 F	Yes	Pregnancy of a recruited researcher.	flexible timesheet; back-up plans and temporary hiring
IND	16 M (including project coordinator) 6 F	Yes	N/A	N/A
KEMEA	5 M (including the unit coordinator) 8 F	In progress	N/A	N/A
SERMAS	10 M; 8 F	No	Pregnancy of a recruited researcher.	Flexible timesheet
NOV	5 M 0 F (before 4 M - 1 F)	Yes	N/A	N/A
HRT	5M 4F	Yes	N/A	N/A
HESE	2M (including tasks coordinators)	Yes	N/A	N/A

Partner	Team composition	Gender Equality Plan	Gender related issues	Adopted strategy
	2F			
PARTICLE	5M 1F	No	N/A	N/A
UMU	7M (researchers) 3F (admin)	Yes	N/A	N/A
ISEMI	3 M, 3 F	No	N/A	N/A
ARATOS.NET	3 M 1 F	Yes	N/A	N/A
Blockchain 2050	4M 3F	Yes	N/A	N/A

Table 3 – GEPs and Teams analysis

As far as other grounds of diversity assessment are concerned, no issues have been identified and therefore addressed and mitigated.

In addition, we asked partners to suggest possible actions to mitigate gender and diversity related gaps. The following propositions have been identified.

- Introduction of specific costs in the budget for family-related issues for recruited staff (e.g., babysitter, caregiver)
- Adoption of selected strategies at University level: flexitime, economic equity
- Make a longer shortlist when recruiting
- Use skills-based assessments
- Adopt Community Principles and a Code of Conduct
- Appoint a Safety Officer
- Mentorship program
- Focus groups
- Balanced recruiting candidate lists
- Give Benefits for Participating in Diversity Programming
- Conduct timely audits

5. DEMO: How to address ethics and diversity compliance in Research and Development sector

The DEMO includes 4 sections to explore how to address ethics and diversity compliance in Research and Development sector: 1. Preparatory activities; 2. Research management; 3. Research Development; 4. Dissemination.

It will be available on the website of VALKYRIES by M24. At this stage a workable checklist will be downloadable by users and stakeholders who will be able to submit it by email for comments.

5.1. Preparatory activities

During preparatory activities the researcher has to start an impact assessment identifying risks that the proposed idea could develop against fundamental rights and in particular against inclusiveness. Therefore, the researcher has to identify proper technical and organisational measures to design fair and accountable solutions by design and by default as well as to build up managing procedures able to ensure ethical values and diversity promotion among the human resources involved in the project. To this end, the following actions shall be undertaken.

In order to assess the proposal in terms of impact on human dignity and non-discrimination, verify if it is required, firstly:

- a. to include an ethical-legal expertise among the team to undertake the ALTAI check-list if you are developing a solution based on Artificial Intelligence
 - i. if yes, allocate resources and justify them
- b. to include the data protection officer to assess the impact on personal data processing
 - i. if yes, allocate resources and justify them
- c. the approval of an ethical committee to test the solution
 - i. if yes, allocate time and resources and justify them

Then:

- d. to develop a workplan including
 - i. a continuous assessment of the impact on fundamental rights
 - ii. the implementation of safeguards to mitigate the identified risks against human dignity and inclusion
 - iii. monitoring and report mechanisms to face unpredicted risks

5.2. Research management

In order to promote equality and diversity in the team:

- a. Apply within the project principles adopted in the institutional Gender Equality Plan / Code of Ethics
- b. Apply measures to encourage an inclusive environment during the life-cycle of the research and development (e.g. work-life balance in the workplan; feminine inclusion and leadership in the governance), by:
 - Mapping gender representation in the team
 - Mapping possible needs in the given need
 - Mapping the different religious-cultural holidays

5.3. Research development

In order to promote equality and diversity in the developed technology:

- a. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data collection and justify them in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- b. Assess the grounds of discrimination in the data processing activities in order to avoid bias in the automated decision-making
- c. Check the data generated by the automated decision-making in order to avoid further bias

5.4. Dissemination

During the dissemination activity the role of ethics and diversity is crucial as the accountable approach could be promoted together with the developed technology. This would increase the trustworthiness among the given technological solution as well as contributing to create standards also in the ethical dimension in terms of inclusiveness and non-discrimination.

Therefore, it will be useful to:

- a. Disseminate disaggregated data on sex in order to highlight possible vulnerabilities/bias or to promote best practice
- b. Promote safeguards and practices developed in the life-cycle of the research to contribute on the standardisation and harmonisation process

6. Conclusions

This deliverable described the VALKYRIES approach towards ethics and diversity compliance, providing a useful demonstrator applicable to all research and innovation contexts during the entire life-cycle of the research.

7. Annex A – References and bibliography

EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en#gender-equality-strategy-2020-2025

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8. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
GEP	Gender equality plan
AI	Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General data protection regulation
EU	European Union
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
ALTAI	Assessment List on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence

Table 4 – Glossary